

Appendix A

Requirement Survey on Tang Poetry Knowledge Service

Dear Sir/Madam:

Hello! We are from Information Integration and Application Laboratory, School of Information Management of Wuhan University. We are currently developing the Tang poetry intelligent knowledge service platform. In order to fully understand the requirements of Tang poetry knowledge service, we conduct a questionnaire survey. We will be very grateful to you for participating in this survey. We hope to receive your strong support and cooperation. This questionnaire is anonymous and all data is used for research and analysis. There is no right or wrong question option, please fill in according to your actual situation. Thank you for your help!

1. Your age group: [Single choice question] *

18 or less 18~25 26~40 41~55 55 or more

2. Your current occupation: [Single choice questions] *

students teacher other

3. Your usual email address (only as a follow-up survey): [fill in the blank]

4. Your research topics in the field of Tang poetry is: [Single choice question] *

History (poet experience, poetry creation background, etc.)

Poetics (genre, rhythm and other poetry creation skills)

Philology (version falsification, literature collation research)

Other _____ *

Here, we provide relevant Tang poetry knowledge service research as a reference:

Tang poetry knowledge service mainly uses advanced computer technology, machine learning, knowledge graph and other mathematical statistics, integrates Tang poetry domain knowledge, and performs semantic association processing on data to assist Tang poetry research. Such as association analysis, knowledge reasoning, etc.

Some of the relevant researches listed below are listed below:

1. Poet's spatio-temporal trajectory.

By combining time and space trajectories, you can view poet experiences and poems by selecting poets and places. For example:

Souyun-- Chronicle map of Tang and Song Dynasties

*

Yes No Not sure

6. Can these knowledge services meet your research needs? [Single choice questions]

*

Very dissatisfied 1 2 3 4 5 Very satisfied

7. Please rate the professionalism of these knowledge services: [Single choice questions]

*

Very unprofessional 1 2 3 4 5 Very professional

8. If you have a professional Tang poetry intelligent knowledge service platform, would you like to try it? [Single choice questions] *

Willing Unwilling Not sure

9. What data do you need in your research? [Multiple choice questions] *

- Poet basic introductions
- Appreciation and comments
- Poet life experience
- Geographic & chronological data
- Other _____ *

10. Where do you collect data? [Multiple choice questions] *

- Paper literature
- Database
- Search engine
- Websites
- Other _____ *

11. Please rate the satisfaction of data needs based on these sources: [matrix scale question] *

	1	2	3	4	5
Paper literature	<input type="radio"/>				
Search engine	<input type="radio"/>				
Websites	<input type="radio"/>				
Database	<input type="radio"/>				

Other	○	○	○	○	○
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The smaller the score, the lower the satisfaction.

12. What difficulties have you encountered in data utilization? [Multiple choice questions] *

- Data collection: _____ *
- Data processing: _____ *
- Data analysis: _____ *
- Data presentation: _____ *
- Other _____ *

13. What function do you want the Tang poetry Knowledge Service to provide?

[Multiple choice questions] *

- Basic knowledge display
- Poet social relationship graph
- Poet spatio-temporal trajectory
- Emotion analysis
- Imagery association
- Semantic query (return to the answer directly)
- Other _____ *

14. Please talk about your vision of the future of intelligent knowledge services in the field of Tang poetry: [fill in the blank]

Appendix B

Evaluation of Tang Poetry Knowledge Service Platform

Dear Sir/Madam:

Hello! We are from Information Integration and Application Laboratory, School of Information Management of Wuhan University. We are currently developing the Tang poetry knowledge service platform. In order to further optimize the design of the platform, we conducted a questionnaire survey. We will be very grateful to you for participating in this survey. I hope to receive your strong support and cooperation. This questionnaire is anonymous. All data is for research and analysis. Please feel free to fill it out. There is no right or wrong question option, please fill in according to your actual

situation. Thank you for your help!

Before filling out the following questionnaire, please visit the website kg.whu.edu.cn to find out the specific information of the "KnowPoetry" platform.

1. Please rate the following indicators (Matrix scale question)

	1	2	3	4	5
Integrity	<input type="radio"/>				
Accuracy	<input type="radio"/>				
Reliability	<input type="radio"/>				
Timeliness	<input type="radio"/>				
Comprehensiveness	<input type="radio"/>				
Comprehensibility	<input type="radio"/>				
Visualization	<input type="radio"/>				
Accessibility	<input type="radio"/>				
Fluency	<input type="radio"/>				
Security	<input type="radio"/>				
Diversity	<input type="radio"/>				
Personalization	<input type="radio"/>				
Social graph function	<input type="radio"/>				
Trajectory map function	<input type="radio"/>				
Knowledge exploration	<input type="radio"/>				

function					
Semantic query function	○	○	○	○	○
Feedback mechanism	○	○	○	○	○

The smaller the score, the lower the satisfaction.

2. Please talk about your views on the “KnowPoetry” platform, we will take every proposal you put forward seriously! [Fill in the blank] *
